

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DAROU-NANSAM****FIRST NAME: YASSER****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 2016 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. The process of academic essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-10)
2. Structure of academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 10-12)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 14, 33-39)
4. Some rules of thumb for writing papers (EUCLID 2021, 14-16)
5. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Doctoral training is a long process of analysis and reflection on a relevant subject, often requiring determination and academic rigor. As part of my doctoral thesis at Euclid University, this first course on ACA-401D provides exciting insights into learning English, especially the difference between American and British English, especially since I come from a French-speaking country. It also guides students towards a solid foundation of academic essay writing using recommended styles. After taking this course, I understood the basic steps in writing an essay and the critical resources required to move from one stage to the next and deliver a thesis that meets international standards.

In this response paper, I will first discuss the process of writing an academic essay, its structure, then the issue of plagiarism, followed by the rules of thumb for writing, and I will finish with style guides.

2) THE PROCESS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

Writing an academic essay can be stressful, especially if the steps to be taken before it starts are not known in advance. For a quick start, it's essential to begin as early as possible (EUCLID 2021, 7). By this, I mean that in the early stages of writing, you need enough time to identify better and structure the ideas to be developed. Also, it is essential to set up a plan for writing the essay to include initial thoughts and ideas on the research topic. If an essay plan is written correctly, it will help determine how to answer the question and what information to use (EUCLID 2021, 7).

Once the writing plan has been established, it is essential to understand the basic steps involved in writing an essay. EUCLID (2021, 8) proposes 11 basic essay writing steps. These steps range from analyzing the question and defining the key terms to writing the essay by hand. The first step concerns the analysis and definition of critical terms (EUCLID 2021, 8). At this stage, depending on the field of intervention and the chosen topic, we need to identify the terms that can help us better understand the selected topic. The second step is to establish points of view on the topic. The third to eleventh steps involve researching the topic, developing a writing plan, organizing ideas, and developing the topic using references to produce a document that considers the rules of academic writing.

Structuring your essay plan is essential to help you get down to writing, focusing on topics relevant to your field of study, with an emphasis on critical thinking to achieve your study objective.

3) THE STRUCTURE OF ACADEMIC ESSAYS

The academic essay begins when the topic is well chosen and the ideas on the theme are sufficiently organized. After these prerequisites, structuring the academic essay enables the concepts to be presented in different document parts. For example, EUCLID (2021, 10) suggests a structure for an essay plan comprising the introduction, body, and conclusion.

An essay begins with the introduction, which gives an orientation to the topic with one or two opening sentences (EUCLID 2021, 10). A good introduction has two parts: (1) several general statements and (2) a thesis statement. The first part of an essay's introductory paragraph often begins by explaining a problem (Oshima and Hogue, 2007). From the explanation of the problem emerge the various statements made by the actors who have written on the topic, as well as the problem statement, which leads to the summary of the essay's roadmap. After the introduction, the essay's body begins, consisting of the development of arguments. The body allows for using relevant examples and specific quotations to support the arguments raised. The final part of the essay is the conclusion. It is an essential part of any academic paper, emphasizing or reaffirming the most critical points in the discussion. It is essential to give future research directions without introducing new information or ideas (EUCLID 2021, 10).

The three structures of academic writing must be mastered for logical reasoning and sound development of arguments, taking into account bibliographical references to avoid plagiarism.

4) PLAGIARISM

Avoiding plagiarism in academic research is essential for a quality academic essay. Plagiarism is presenting work or ideas from another source as your own, with or without the original author's consent, by incorporating it into your work without full acknowledgment. Plagiarism occurs when the author uses a source of information without crediting the author (EUCLID 2021, 34). It is, therefore, essential to recognize plagiarism to avoid it in academic writing.

In academic work, plagiarism takes two forms. Firstly, plagiarism occurs when words from a source are used without quotation marks (EUCLID 2021, 14). Consequently, it is essential to go beyond a footnote and use quotation marks when the words of a source are quoted. Secondly, plagiarism occurs when a source's ideas are repeated without footnoting. Plagiarism is generally punished. According to Berlinck (2011), sanctions for academic plagiarism can intervene at two levels: the level of the teacher-student relationship and the level of the student-institution relationship. Berlinck (2011) asserts that, in general, sanctions instituted by teachers tend to be milder, although this tendency is not a rule. The author goes on to say that, in general, teacher-imposed sanctions take the form of verbal or written warnings or a change in grade or final evaluation of a course or student activity.

Plagiarism is a complex concept to understand to produce a document that respects the rules of academic ethics.

5) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

Rules of thumb for writing are necessary to approach the development of an academic essay better. I have noted that the opening paragraph must highlight the central thesis. According to EUCLID (2021, 13), papers should be critical of existing theories.

The basic rule is that the ideas expressed should reflect the words used. When developing ideas, it is essential to avoid long sentences or paragraphs, which often cause the reader to lose track or even get confused at some point. The spirit of synthesis is therefore encouraged when writing an academic essay. Also, repeating the exact words risks making the writing dull and clumsy. Regarding argumentation, it is best to respect the opinions of authors who have written on the subject. Generally, a passage should only be quoted when it addresses your topic (EUCLID 2021, 13). Authors whose ideas are used should be cited in the document.

6) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide is an international standard for writing in English-language documents. According to the source, the “instruction manual” guides document writing, syntax, grammar, and formatting, particularly in specific academic disciplines. Style guides also include rules for formatting citations and references. By setting standards that authors must follow, style guides help to ensure intra- and interdisciplinary cohesion and knowledge sharing. It also documents your approach as a writer to maintain consistency (EUCLID 2021, 41).

In this part of the course, I would like to point out that EUCLID recommends using American English, but both recognized rules are acceptable (EUCLID 2021, 41). EUCLID recommends Chicago rules (Turabian), but other internationally recognized rules can be accepted. I have used the American Psychological Association (APA) style when writing academic dissertations and have found it easy to use. APA style forms the basis of effective scientific communication, helping writers present their ideas concisely and inclusively. When the style works best, ideas flow logically, sources are credited appropriately, and articles are organized predictably.

7) CONCLUSION

This first ACA-401D course teaches the essential notions for any researcher to get off to a good start in writing a scientific paper. It helped me realize the depth of a thesis and what awaits me throughout this PhD in climate change and sustainability. Period 1 also broadened my knowledge of English, especially the variants between British and American English. Through this course, I assimilated notions on the basics of essay writing, punctuation, plagiarism, and style rules. These notions will enable me to tackle future courses better.

REFERENCES

Cleenerwerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.